

icant, the data indicated that at 29 and 58 kg N/ha, SCU and USG were more efficient than all other sources. At 87 kg N/ha, SCU, USG, and split-applied prilled urea yielded similarly and more than

basal prilled urea and LCU. LCU was least efficient at all N levels.

Zn deficiency symptoms increased with higher basal SCU and USG N applications. Drought also affected those treat-

ments more adversely.

Results suggest that application of 58 kg N/ha as SCU or USG produces best yields in drought-prone areas with Zn-deficient calcareous soil. □

Nitrogen fertilization and spacing to maximize upland rice yield

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Upland rice is a major crop in eastern Uttar Pradesh, but yields are low because of drought, weeds, poor agronomic practices, and lack of locally adapted improved varieties with good yield potential and high nutrient use efficiency. In 1976 we tested the effect of row spacing and nutrient supply on grain yield of Narendra 1 (IET2232), a semidwarf upland rice.

The crop was grown under natural upland conditions on sandy loam soils at Faizabad at 3 row spacings — 15, 20, and 25 cm — and nitrogen levels — 0, 40, and 80 kg/ha. Fourteen kg P and 25 kg K/ha were applied to all plots. The field was tilled after the first rain in early Jul, and 100 kg seed/ha was direct-seeded in rows. The crop was hand weeded. The experiment was repeated in 1977 and 1978. Weekly rainfall at Faizabad from Jun to Oct 1976 and 1978 is in the table. Total rainfall during the crop season is about 1,000 mm, but is interrupted by drought spells. In 1977 the crop failed because of drought.

Grain yield increased sharply with increased nitrogen, regardless of row spa-

Effect of nitrogen levels and row spacings on upland rice yield, Faizabad, India.

Weekly rainfall distribution during crop season at Faizabad, India

Month	Year	Rainfall (mm)				
		Wk 1	Wk 2	Wk 3	Wk 4	Total
Jun	1976	0	21.6	0	8.6	30.6
	1978	0	55.6	61.2	15.2	132.0
Jul	1976	0	81.8	97.6	32.0	211.4
	1978	2.6	3.4	420.0	75.2	501.2
Aug	1976	109.6	218.0	133.6	77.6	538.8
	1978	13.6	115.2	39.2	12.4	180.4
Sep	1976	0	214.6	13.6	84.6	312.8
	1978	33.2	57.8	41.0	64.0	196.0
Oct	1976	0	20.6	0	0	20.6
	1978	15.2	0	0	0	15.2

Total rainfall = 1113.8 in 1976, 1024.8 in 1978.

cing (see figure). Yield increased from 1.6 t/ha at 0 kg N to 3.6 t/ha at 40 kg N and to 4.1 t/ha at 80 kg N/ha in 1976. Re-

sponse to N was similar in 1978. The 20-cm spacing between rows produced maximum grain yields at 40 and 80 kg N/ha. □

Effect of amendments and presubmergence on Fe and Mn availability in sodic soil and on rice yield

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A field experiment evaluated the effect of adding 12.5 t gypsum/ha, pyrite (equivalent to gypsum on sulfur basis), 30 t farmyard manure/ha, 30 t rice husk/ha at 0 and 30 days submergence prior to transplanting of rice on Fe and Mn availability and rice yield. The experiment

was replicated 4 times in a split-plot design on highly sodic sandy soil with pH 10.6, exchangeable sodium percentage

(ESP) 94, exchangeable Ca + Mg 0.4 meq/100 g soil, organic carbon 0.26%, CaCO₃ 2.75%, CEC 10.0 meq/100 g soil,

Table 1. Effect of duration of pretransplanting submergence and amendments on rice grain yield.

Duration of pre-planting submergence (d)	Grain yield (t/ha)					
	Control	Gypsum	Pyrite	Farmyard manure	Rice husk	Mean
0	0.08	5.19	4.81	3.29	2.70	3.21
30	0.18	5.58	5.43	5.52	4.52	4.24
Mean	0.13	5.38	5.12	4.40	3.61	

CD at P = 0.05, Amendments = 0.23; Submergence = 0.13; Amendments × submergence = 0.29.

Table 2. Changes in Mn, Fe, soil pH, and ESP in submerged sodic soil as affected by amendments during the growth period of rice crop (av of 4 replications).

Amendment	Duration of submergence prior to planting (d)	Extractable Mn ^a				Extractable Fe				Soil pH after crop harvest	ESP
		A (ppm)	B (ppm)	C (ppm)	D (ppm)	A (ppm)	B (ppm)	C (ppm)	D (ppm)		
None (control)	0	2.2	11.9	11.8	10.5	3.0	14.5	14.5	14.0	10.3	82.8
	30	12.5	11.6	11.5	10.8	12.9	15.6	16.0	15.5	10.1	81.0
Gypsum	0	2.5	14.0	15.5	15.0	2.7	16.8	22.0	18.0	9.5	37.5
	30	15.0	16.5	16.8	15.8	15.5	20.6	25.5	22.6	9.3	35.2
Pyrite	0	2.0	17.5	18.0	17.5	3.5	31.5	32.6	30.8	9.6	39.6
	30	17.8	18.5	18.5	18.0	32.8	33.0	32.6	31.6	9.4	37.5
Farmyard manure	0	2.6	62.8	70.0	68.8	3.4	60.5	64.0	60.5	9.9	72.5
	30	65.7	68.6	78.5	70.5	59.8	65.8	65.5	62.0	9.8	62.0
Rice husk	0	2.4	40.5	48.0	45.5	3.5	44.5	45.3	40.6	10.0	74.5
	30	48.5	50.6	54.6	50.1	45.6	48.5	48.0	45.3	9.9	70.1

^aA = at the time of transplanting, B = 30 days after transplanting, C = 60 days after transplanting, D = 90 days after transplanting.

and gypsum requirement 25 t/ha at Gudha experimental farm of CSSRI, Karnal.

Amendments were added at flooding except for pyrite, which was applied 3 days before flooding under moist conditions to ensure proper oxidation. Soil was submerged until Jaya was transplanted in standing water 18 Jul 1982, and maintained thus throughout the crop period. Urea at 150 kg N/ha and 40 kg ZnSO₄/ha were applied to the crop. One-half the N

and all the Zn were applied at transplanting. The remaining N was topdressed in 2 equal splits at 3 and 6 weeks of crop growth. The crop was harvested 30 Oct 1982.

The effect on grain yield of 30 d pre-submergence was significant for farmyard manure and rice husk where there had not been previous flooding (Table 1). Gypsum and pyrite reduced pH and ESP more (Table 2) and produced higher

yields than other treatments at 0 days submergence, but farmyard manure produced equal yields at 30 d pre-submergence.

Extractable Fe and Mn increased with duration of submergence in the following order: farmyard manure, rice husk, pyrite, and gypsum (Table 2). The effect of pre-submergence was conspicuous up to 60 d of crop growth but remained constant or declined slightly beyond 60 d. □

Effect of USG placement and planting geometry on yield of random-planted rice

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We evaluated the feasibility of urea supergranule (USG) deep placement in randomly transplanted rice, a planting practice followed by most Indian farmers. We also compared deep placement at 24.5- × 24.5-cm and 20- × 20-cm spacing as an economy measure, and broadcast application of USG vs prilled urea. Treatments were in a randomized block design with three replications.

In random transplanting, deep placement increased Jaya yield by 0.4 t/ha and Govind yield by 1.1 t/ha (Table 1) over yields with broadcast fertilizer. Yield for 6-7 seedlings/hill spaced at 24.5 × 24.5 cm equaled that of 4 seedlings/hill at 20- × 20-cm spacing. The wider spacing could reduce hand point placement cost by 15% (labor). USG yields were signif-

Table 1. Deep placement vs broadcast application of USG at 60 kg N/ha under different planting geometries during 1982 rainy season at Pantnagar, India.

Planting geometry	Seedlings per hill ^a	Grain yield (t/ha)	
		Broadcast ^b	Placement
<i>Jaya (medium duration)</i>			
Random (farmers' practice)	6-7	5.0	5.4
Row 24.5 × 24.5 cm	6-7	4.2	5.6
Row 20 × 20 cm recommended practice	4 ^c	4.1	4.9
<i>Govind (short duration)</i>			
Random - farmers' practice	6-7	3.5	4.6
Row 24.5 × 24.5 cm	6-7	3.7	4.3
Row 20 × 20 cm, recommended practice	4 ^c	4.3	4.5
Mean		4.1	4.9
LSD 5% broadcast vs placement			0.4
CV (%)			12

^aTo give 100 seedlings/m². ^bUSG was dissolved and mixed because of light rains following application, however, it was not incorporated. ^cThe seedling number was increased from 2 (normal) to 4/hill due to late planting (30 Jul). Late plantings are common with poor farmers.

Table 2. Broadcast and incorporation of USG vs prilled urea at 60 kg N/ha in very late planting during 1982 rainy season at Pantnagar, India.

N fertilizer	Grain yield (t/ha)
Urea supergranule	2.1
Urea	1.5
LSD 5%	0.5
CV	8%

icantly superior to those with prilled urea for broadcast and incorporation application (Table 2); however, yield was only 2 t/ha because the crop was late. □